

**AN ASSESSMENT OF PONZI SCHEMES IN NIGERIA WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF THE
NIGERIAN LEGAL FRAMEWORK**

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ABSTRACT

Over the last five years, financial frauds have increased greatly in Nigeria leading to catastrophic implications. One of these fraudulent financial schemes, is the ponzi scheme. This paper seeks to address the different legislative frameworks that relate to ponzi scheme. It employs a doctrinal approach, analyzing statutes and case laws with a major emphasis on Investment and Securities Act 2025. This paper argues that ponzi scheme is both a civil wrong, and a financial crime, citing sections from Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) and Investment and Securities Act (ISA). It recommends that due to the large sum of money usually stolen during the fraudulent ponzi act, the option of fine should be removed from the imprisonment sentence.

Key words: ponzi scheme, financial crime, legal framework.

INTRODUCTION

The Norrenberger Financial Investment Scheme estimated that as at 2022, Nigeria had lost over N300bn to Ponzi Schemes in the space of five years.¹ The effect of this alarming result is beyond only financial loss of property. It causes other issues like loss of trust, and discrediting the financial market, reducing the willingness of potential investors. For a country like Nigeria with an already staggering economy, the impact of the reluctance of investors will be very notable and disastrous.² Beyond these, are mental and emotional impact it can have on its victims. The emotional impact of Ponzi Scheme is so severe, that some women whose husband participated in it testified to likelihood of it accelerating their husband's death. Many other victims of ponzi schemes fell into depression.³

Ponzi Scheme has been in Nigeria for quite a long time: as far back as the early 1900s, but its prevalence has taken a rise in the past few years. A significant time in this rise is 2016, when the Mavrodial Monidial Movement-MMM was introduced into Nigeria. Capitalizing on promise of high returns, MMM was able to capture the attention and willingness of many Nigerians, who invested their property into it. However like other ponzi schemes, it crashed after 18 months of its introduction into the Nigeria Market. Another occurrence of the ruthless ponzi scheme attack is the very recent (as at when this paper was written) Cbex. Investors lost over N1.3TRN to Cbex.⁴ Also, apart from the MMM and Cbex, other Ponzi schemes have been prevalent in

¹ Woyimo Amakoromo, State Regulations and Prevention of Ponzi Schemes in Nigeria (2024 Research Gate) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382175633_STATE_REGULATION_AND_PREVALENCE_OF_PONZI_SCHEMES_IN_NIGERIA?utm_source=twitter&utm_meta1=eHNsLVFPS0lpbE1ydThwQXhIU1JiVXNkLzJtek0yNHhJWnEzeVBjVGx5aTINdzFGeGY0K2svUE5qRHJDTjUrMkU5UTJnNmtTU1d3amdzy0tsN0FRRWxjMyt0QnM%3D> accessed 15th April, 2025

² Solomon Lartey, Impact of Ponzi Scheme on Financial Market and Investor Trusts Globally (2024 Research Gate) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383785630_The_Impact_of_Ponzi_Schemes_on_Financial_Markets_and_Investor_Trust_Globally?utm_source=twitter&utm_meta1=eHNsLTJ2ZU13VGxaOEdvZXV2N2o2R2MyeFV6eUJRbnAxRDY5eXVjT2RJWHU3KzFGZDBuUmtJdWZTemRCcU0yMXNjNIFuNkRhZkFsQ3hsazNjLzk3VHJnQ0ZQQ11%3D> accessed 15th April, 2025

³ Eldad Lev, 'Main Implications and Reactions for the Ponzi Scheme Victims', (2022), Issue 24, Journal of Public Administration, Finance, and Law, 99.

⁴ TVC News "CBEX Crash". YouTube, uploaded by TVC News, 16th April, 2025 <https://youtu.be/cW-DYt-lIuw?si=BFW0urPV4AQJ2AQ>

Nigeria like the Ultimate Cyclor, Zar Fund, Get Help World Wide.

The law has a vital role to play to curb the proliferation of these schemes. If the law stays silent ignoring its prevalence, there are two effects it can have: The first is that there is a risk of contributors remaining vulnerable to exploitation. The second is that the citizens gets frustrated and resort to illegal self help measures. None of the options should be risked and since the law is an instrument of order, peace, and justice, it is trite that the law interferes.

CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF PONZI SCHEME

A ponzi scheme is an investment, where the funds of new members (contributors) are used to pay old members and it often crash, where there is reduction in flow of new contributors. Miebaka Nabiebu defines it as 'when a fraudulent individual or entity collects funds from new investors and uses those funds to pay returns to earlier investors, rather than generating legitimate profits.'⁵ The Investment and Securities Act 2025 defined it as any investment scheme that pays existing contributors with funds collected from new contributors to the scheme promising high returns with little or no risk⁶. Ponzi scheme is an investment, where the originator never made any real investment, to generate income. This is why the owner of the ponzi relies on the income of new investors to be able to fund old investors.

Another fraudulent investment similar to the Ponzi Scheme, but should not be mixed up with it, is the pyramid scheme. While ponzi scheme involves the investors making an investment and they are paid a particular agreed sum, pyramid scheme involves the participants earning money as they bring new contributors to the scheme. Both ponzi and pyramid schemes are fraudulent, and their differences are so minute that they can be mistaken, one for another.

FINANCIAL CRIMES

Financial Crimes in its simplest form are crimes that relates to financial activities. They are

⁵ Miebaka Nabiebu *The Law of Financial Crimes* (Lagos State: Princeton & Associate Publishing Co. Ltd, 2024) p.136

⁶ Investment and Securities Act 2025 s.195(3)(a)

crimes that are against property, committed by individuals and organizations to obtain a personal or business advantage.⁷ Federal Bureau of Investigation (2005) described them as being characterized by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust and are not dependent on application of physical force or violence. Some common examples of financial crimes are: money laundering, embezzlement, and insider trade to mention a few. Financial crimes are not limited to illegal acts; they also include illegal financial omissions like tax evasion. Financial crimes are also not limited to crimes against assets in their liquid form. They cover a wide range of other crimes like crimes against financial instruments like securities, or other properties are financial crimes and identity theft or falsifying records to gain undue financial advantage(s).⁸

Financial crimes are investigated and prosecuted by the government bodies, saddled with that function. Some of these government bodies in Nigeria are: Economic and Financial Crimes Commission, (EFCC) Central Bank of Nigeria, (CBN) and Financial Action Task Force. These bodies work in line with various statutory documents like; Investment and Securities Act, Nigeria Money Laundering Act. Also, there are some laws that while they don't solely nor mainly focus on financial crimes, they address and make provisions against financial crimes, because the crimes they seek to address cannot thrive without financial sponsorship. An example of these laws, is the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK RELATED TO PONZI SCHEME

There is no particular legislative document dedicated to Ponzi Scheme in Nigeria, however ponzi scheme is addressed under a plethora of statutes and case laws. The foremost law addressing ponzi Scheme in Nigeria is the Investment and Securities Act 2025 (which repealed the Investment and Securities Act 2007). ISA makes ponzi scheme an offence, punishable with 10 years imprisonment. Apart from ISA, ponzi schemes fall under both civil wrongs and criminal offences under other statutory documents and case laws.

⁷ Agus Sudjianto, 'Statistical Method for Fighting Financial Crimes', (2010) Vol.52, Technometrics, p.5

⁸ Unit21, 'Financial Crime' <<https://www.unit21.ai/fraud-aml-dictionary/financial-crime>> accessed 16 April 2025.

CRIMINAL ASPECT

As mentioned earlier, no particular statutory document is dedicated to prohibition of ponzi schemes. In fact, only the Investment and Securities Act (ISA) 2025 expressly mentioned ponzi and pyramid schemes.⁹ However, ponzi schemes are made up of elements crimes found in different laws.

The basis of ponzi schemes being criminal can be found in the Criminal Code. The criminal code defines and classifies an offence as 'obtaining by false pretenses'. This crime is committed when a person with the intent to defraud, obtains from any other person, anything capable of being stolen or induces any other person to deliver to any person anything capable of being stolen.¹⁰ For a person to be said to have obtained by false pretense, the ownership of the property must have been induced to be transferred to the inducer, under the inducement. The implication of this is that if a person only induces the transfer of possession, such person cannot be guilty of obtaining by false pretenses. However, caution must be taken when observing the previous sentence. Ownership should be what is induced to be transferred doesn't mean it should be what was transferred. Thus, if a person induces another to transfer ownership but the induced transfers only possession, the offence has still been committed.

Ponzi scheme already matches the transfer of ownership from the contributors to the owners or the inducement by the contributors.. In the case of **kole Bello v. FRN**,¹¹ the court listed elements of false pretense to be: pretence, pretence emanating from the defendant, false pretense, the defendant knowing of its falsity or did not believe in its truth, an intention to defraud, the thing is capable of being stolen, and the defendant induced the owner to transfer the property. Ponzi scheme matches all the elements. The promise of high returns on investment is a false pretense,

⁹ Investment and Securities Act 2025 s.195(3)

¹⁰ Criminal Code s.419

¹¹ Bello v. Federal Republic of Nigeria [2018] CA/L/1105C/2011 LER. Available at: <https://legalpediaonline.com/kole-bello-v-federal-republic-of-nigeria/>.

emanating from the defendants (the operators), and the property transferred which is money, is capable of being stolen. Therefore, the operators of ponzi schemes are guilty of obtaining by false pretenses.

Fortunately, ponzi and pyramid schemes are now expressly mentioned by the ISA Act. This is to clear any ambiguity in determining if it is a crime or not. S195(1) empowers the Security and Exchange Commission to ' enter and seal up all prohibited schemes and shall obtain an order of court to freeze and forfeit all assets'.¹² the third subsection of this section went ahead to state that the prohibited schemes means ponzi and pyramid schemes and the fourth subsection makes operators and promoters of such prohibited schemes guilty of an offense, giving rise to liability of ten years imprisonment or fine of N5,000,000 or both.¹³

The provision of this section makes something obvious, and that is the fact that ponzi scheme is illegal. However, there may be some areas of contention. The first is that since operators of ponzi schemes do not register the schemes to be a juristic person, when can they be liable? Can they only be liable when they are in operation or when an operation is just concluded and being investigated upon, or they can be liable when they are known as promoters and operators, even if they are not carrying out any operation, and have no pending investigation of operation?

It seem to me that they will be liable only when they are in operation or where they have pending investigation of operation. This is because convicting them based on former records seem to do two things that are in contradiction with the law. The first is; if they have been convicted separately for past ponzi acts, it will be double jeopardy to convict them again. The second is that convicting them for being ponzi operators but for not any specific operation at that time, will amount to conviction based on evidence of bad character, which is generally not admissible. admissible.

The second issue posed is the issue of promoters of ponzi and pyramid schemes. Most times, the

¹² Investment and Securities Act s.195(1)

¹³ Ibid s.195(4)

promoters of these schemes are victims of the fraud themselves. They do it either out of loyalty and trust to the scheme or because of promise of higher returns. In cases like these, will the promoters still be liable?

It seems to me that the answer to this is somewhat clear, and that the answer is no. This is fundamentally premised on the basic conditions for a crime to have been committed in the first place, for a crime to be properly constituted, it must have both guilty act (*actus reus*) and guilty mind (*mens rea*)¹⁴ and both of them must be contemporaneous. So, if the promoters did that without having the intention of promoting not just the ponzi scheme, they did a guilty act but without a guilty mind and this cannot be liable.

CIVIL ASPECT.

This aspect of this paper will be commenced with S58(1) and 59 of BOFIA. These sections make no person permitted to carry on financial business in Nigeria other than insurance stock exchange unless it is fully incorporated in Nigeria and holds a valid license granted by the Central Bank of Nigeria. (CBN)¹⁵ Apart from imprisonment and fine already discussed in the criminal aspect, such financial business is to collect the license within six months, or a court injunction to stop the enterprise will be issued.

Furthermore, ponzi scheme is wrong on the basis of contract. Fraudulent misrepresentation is one of the things that can give rise to damages or termination of contract, depending on how fundamental it is. One may ask how ponzi scheme is a contract but it is. The basic elements of a contract are offer, acceptance, and consideration. The owner makes an offer to the contributor or an invitation to treat, which the contributor makes the offer. The other party agrees. The part where people may pose the contract question the most is the issue of consideration. But then, there is consideration. The consideration is the money the contributors are asked to drop initially or subsequently. It doesn't matter that the owner promises them a high return without them performing any other obligation, as consideration doesn't need to be adequate to be sufficient.

¹⁴ C.O Okonkwo and Naish, 'The Legal Elements of an Offence', [ed] Criminal Law in Nigeria (United Kingdom: Safari Books (Export) Limited 2018) p.45

¹⁵ *ibid* s.58(1) and 59

The fact that they are giving their money is enough for consideration and that makes it a contract.

In a case like this where the issue of consideration may not be so clear, it is good to know what the consideration will be and what it will not be. The Longman Dictionary of Law defines consideration as that which is actually given or accepted in return for a promise.¹⁶ In the case of ponzi scheme, the initial invested fund or subsequently invested one is the consideration. This is because that is what is given in exchange for the promise of high returns, and no one will be paid or promised a higher returns without making the investment. However, the implication of the definition of consideration is that in ponzi scheme, it doesn't cover any personal cost the contributor used to achieve the contract. This can include the cost of data spent, time, or energy. This is because while they are end to the consideration, they are not the consideration in themselves.

A question may come to mind. Isn't it an illegal contract and should be void on the basis of illegality? But then, it is illegal because a party decided not to fulfill his part of the contract. The contract was not illegal *ab initio*. The aggrieved party may not even know that such is being in an illegal scheme nor that the transactions will end up as a ponzi scheme. Therefore, the contract cannot be vitiated on the basis on illegality. Instead, the owner can be liable for fraudulent misrepresentation.

CONCLUSION

The issue of ponzi scheme is a serious one in Nigeria. The fact that MMM came and carted funds away from many people and people still fall victim of schemes like it shows that it is an issue that needs to be addressed seriously and urgently. One way this can be done is through legal regulations. On this note, the effort of the National Assembly and the president, on making the present Investment and Securities Act address the issue expressly is very commendable. However, enforcement and public awareness should also be taken very seriously, so that the perpetrators of this fraudulent act can be brought to face justice.

¹⁶ L.B. Curzon and P.H. Richards The Longman Dictionary of Law, [ed] (England: Pearson Education Limited, 2007) p.123

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommended;

- I. That due to the amount usually carted away by the owners and promoters of Ponzi Scheme, the option of fine should be removed from imprisonment sentence.
- II. That due to the high prevalence and risk of ponzi schemes, a statutory document should be dedicated to it
- III. That more awareness should be made, so that victims of ponzi scheme can know the remedies available for them in law.